

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID-PLC3 CELLS DIFFERENTIATION
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Version:	01	
Valid from:	01.09.2025	

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1. Goal and Area of Application

When infecting PLC3 cell line with HEV for evaluating the antiviral effect of a compound, the PLC3 cells have to be differentiated.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

CMPs Compounds

PPC Porphyrin-Peptide Conjugates

3. Method

3.1 General

This SOP describes the differentiation protocol for PLC3 cells before HEV infection and assessment of antiviral compounds.

PLC3 cells are a subclone of PLC/PRF/5 hepatoma cell line, commonly used for HEV replication studies. Differentiation of these cells leads to polarisation that better reproduces the hepatocyte architecture *in vivo*, further increasing the susceptibility of these cells to HEV infection and promoting viral replication. PLC3 cells enter differentiation by keeping them in culture flasks without passing them. Only the medium is changed three times a week for 10 days.

3.2 Information for consommables / chemicals /equipment

Product name	Supplier	Ordering n°
DMEM High Glucose	Gibco	61965059
Fetal Bovine Serum	e.g. Gibco	e.g. 10270-106
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Gibco	15140
Sterile 96 well culture plate, flat bottom (polystyrene)	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. 353072
PLC3 cells (a clone of PLC/PRF/5 cells)	Gift from CIIL, Center for Infection & Immunity of Lille, France	

3.3 Procedure : PLC3 cells differentiation

6.10^5 PLC3 cells are seeded in T75 flasks in 10 mL DMEM + 10% FBS + 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin

The medium is renewed every 2 to 3 days.

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Cells are kept in culture for at least 10 days without passage. A change in cell shape is then observed, indicating their differentiation.

These cells can then be used to study HEV infection and test the antiviral effect of compounds.